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Gelatine Extraction from Sea Chicken Fish (*Canthidermis maculata*) By-Products for Waste Reduction and Produce Value Added Products in The Seafood Industry

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Introduction

Fish processing recovers only 20-50% of raw materials as edible product, while 50-80% discarded as by product such as skin, bones, heads and viscera. A small portion of these by-products is used to produce low-value products such as fertiliser, fish feed and fish oil. The major portion is dumped causing environmental, social and economic problems. Fish skin constitutes a main component of these by-products with gelatine accounting for the highest component of protein within it. Gelatine is an important biopolymer used in sectors such as food, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and photography. Gelatine primarily arises from pig skin (46%), bovine hide (29.4%), and pork & cattle bones (23.1%). In 2007 Fish gelatine constituted less than 1.5% of the total production but had doubled since 2002 emphasizing the growing importance of non-mammalian sources in gelatine manufacturing (Gómez-Guillén *et al.*, 2009). Sea chicken fish with its tough skin and bones is therefore suitable as raw material for gelatine manufacture. Presently only the meat is used resulting to up to 51% wastage level. Therefore, utilization of this type of fish's skin and bones would reduce waste and increase value from discarded components (Arpi *et al.*, 2016). This research assessed how two acid pre-treatments affected the physiochemical properties of extracted gelatine during gelatine production from skins of sea-chicken fish.

Methodology

The skins were precisely cut into small pieces measuring 2cm by 2cm. These pieces were then carefully stored in polyethylene bags at a temperature of -20°C for preservation. The skins were thawed, and their weight was recorded (100 g), followed by a water wash. To remove non-collagenous proteins, the skins underwent a one-hour immersion in 0.1 M NaOH solution at a ratio of 1:6 (w/v) with continuous stirring at 125 rpm. Then, the skins were compressed for 5 minutes in a cotton mesh covered funnel, and the washing procedure was repeated twice. The next step

treated the fish skins with HCl or acetic acid (CH₃COOH) solutions at concentrations of 0.15 M and 0.2 M (1:6 w/v ratio) under constant stirring at 125 rpm for 1 hour. The acid solution was then drained off, and this acid treatment process was repeated twice (Mazorra-manzano *et al.*, 2018). The acid pre-treatments were followed by extracting gelatine using distilled water (1:6, w/v) at 60 °C for 3 hours. The solution containing residual skins was subjected to filtration using a Büchner funnel equipped with Whatman no. 4 filter paper (Mazorra-manzano *et al.*, 2018). The recovered gelatine solutions were allowed to cool to room temperature, and their total volume was measured. Finally, the gelatine solutions were dried with vacuum oven at 50°C. Then quality of the extracted gelatine was tested

Results/Findings

This research assessed the impact of HCl and CH₃COOH effect, at 0.15 M, and 0.2 M, on extraction yield, gel strength, viscosity, colour, pH, protein, ash, minerals, melting point of sea chicken fish skin gelatines.

Table 1 :Physicochemical properties of gelatine from sea chicken fish obtained from different acid treatments and commercial sample

Treatments	HCL 0.15	HCL 0.20	CH ₃ COOH 0.15	CH ₃ COOH 0.20	COMMERCIAL
Yield (%)	8.99	7.35	7.18	5.41	-
Gel strength (N)	0.539±0.0128 ^{ab}	0.5830±0.0496 ^b	0.490±0.0069 ^a	0.509±0.0087 ^{ab}	0.042±0.0003 ^c
Viscosity (cP)	3.21±0.176 ^a	4.51±0.99 ^c	3.95±0.408 ^a	4.51±1.422 ^b	4.55±0.609 ^c
pH	6.0667±0.31 ^a	5.25±0.01 ^b	4.94±0.06 ^c	4.7067±0.023 ^d	6.04±0.052 ^a
Melting point (°C)	27±1.000 ^a	25.33±0.577 ^a	25.33±1.155 ^a	22.33±0.577 ^b	22.67±0.577 ^b
Proximate analysis					
Crude protein (%)	74.38±2.175 ^a	75.61±0.175 ^a	82.75±1.100 ^b	72.70±1.515 ^a	88±0.000 ^c
Ash (%)	0.0831±0.0068 ^a	0.0689±0.0007 ^b	0.0623±0.0022 ^{bc}	0.0645±0.003 ^{bc}	0.0467±0.0004 ^c
Ca (mg/kg)	0 ^a	2.753±0.394 ^b	13.162±0.355 ^c	10.438±0.849 ^d	7.805±1.099 ^e
Mg (mg/kg)	1.738±0.1157 ^a	3.720±0.0121 ^b	12.325±0.0594 ^c	18.147±0.7823 ^d	0.43±0.0025 ^e
P(mg/kg)	53.821±3.199 ^a	82.527±1.550 ^b	59.308±1.297 ^c	74.616±0.283 ^d	0 ^e
Colour					
Colour L*	4.0767±0.087 ^a	6.7133±0.480 ^b	6.5033±1.237 ^b	9.3967±0.679 ^c	11.4±0.981 ^c
Colour a*	-5.447±0.055 ^a	-2.94±0.64 ^a	-5.8±0.41 ^a	-4.877±0.080 ^a	-7.393±1.065 ^c
Colour b*	8.83±1.61 ^a	5.89±0.18 ^b	4.95±0.52 ^b	6.78±0.35 ^{ab}	18.67±0.27 ^c

Discussion

Factors such as acid content, extracting temperature, soaking time and extraction duration play pivotal roles in gelatine production. Increasing acid concentration led to a decrease in yield. Gelatine strength is important for quality and applications, increase with acid concentration. HCl exhibited higher gel strength values compared to CH₃COOH, particularly at 0.2 M concentration, where maximal gel strength was achieved ($0.5830 \pm 0.0247\text{N}$, $P < 0.05$). Compared to the commercial sample, all acid-treated gelatines from sea chicken showed notably high gel strength. High gel strength indicates superior quality. Variations in gel strength values of the two acid gelatines can be linked to the specific amino acid profiles of collagen sources and the distribution of various components present in the manufactured product (Mazorra-manzano *et al.*, 2018).

Viscosity, another characteristic of gelatine in the industry, with high viscosity gelatines producing tough, extensible gels while low viscosity gelatines result in short, brittle gels (Mazorra-manzano *et al.*, 2018). Low viscosity gelatine solutions tend to produce thin gels, while high viscosity solutions yield stiff, extensible gels with greater commercial value. In the study, the viscosity of gelatine increased with higher acid concentrations. The viscosity for the samples ranged from 3.21 to 4.51 cP. Gelatine extracted from sea chicken fish skin typically exhibited viscosity values within the standard commercial range of 2.0 to 7.0 cP (Rafieian *et al.*, 2015).

The colour values ("L" and "a") of gelatine samples increasing with higher acid concentration. The treatments exhibited yellowish and greenish hues, with no presence of blue or red tones. Inorganic, proteinaceous, and mucosubstance impurities introduced or retained during the extraction process contribute to the coloration of gelatine.

The pH values of gelatine samples ranging from 6.07 to 4.70 for sea chicken fish gelatine. According to the Gelatine Quality Standard (GMIA, 2012), the recommended pH range is between 3.8 and 5.5. This requirement was satisfied by the acid pre-treatments using 0.20 M HCl, 0.15 M CH₃COOH, and 0.20 M CH₃COOH, ensuring compliance with industry standards. The melting point range from (22-27) °C Lower melting point in fish gelatine was associated with enhanced flavour release, improved smell, and better control of texture and flavour release during product mastication (Koli *et al.*, 2013).

Conclusion

This study evaluated the impact of hydrochloric acid (HCl) and acetic acid (CH₃COOH) concentrations (0.15 M and 0.2 M). pre-treated with HCl and CH₃COOH (0.15M and 0.2M) gave the highest yield (8.99%), at the same time 0.15 CH₃COOH achieved the highest protein content (82.75%). Additionally, the pH and viscosity levels were 4.94 and 3.95 cP, respectively, meeting standard requirements. Additionally, gel strength from all treatments exceeded that of commercial gelatine, indicating its potential for various food-related applications. Notably, HCl at 0.2 M exhibited the highest gel strength (0.5583 N). Overall, the extraction of gelatine from sea chicken fish skin was found to be suitable and cost-effective, utilizing discarded waste product effectively.

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